

Beta Gallium Oxide Nanowires and Nano-sheets growth by Chemical Vapour Deposition

T. Rajesh, G. Sasikala*, S. Sumathi, S. Suguna and R. Jayavel

Crystal Growth Centre, Anna University, Chennai-600025

Corresponding author email and mobile no: *sasikalaganapathycgc@gmail.com and 9952954566

Abstract

One dimensional and Two dimensional semiconductor nanostructures have taken much consideration of researchers due to its potential device applications [1-2]. The wide band gap (E_g : 4.9 eV) and Monoclinic structured beta gallium oxide (β -Ga₂O₃) is an important material for the applications including TCO, optical emitter for UV, and gas sensors because of its good chemical stability at high temperature [3].

In this work, we have synthesized β -Ga₂O₃ nanowires and nano-sheets on substrates by the method of chemical vapour deposition at the temperature of 900° C have been reported. Gallium metal serving as the gallium source and argon gas helps to carry the oxygen gas for the nanostructures growth. Initially Au was sputtered on cleaned substrates, which act as the catalyst to assist the growth. X-ray diffraction (XRD) has been used to study the crystal structures of these nanowires and nano-sheets. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) images show the formation of nanowires and sheets. Diffuse Reflectance spectroscopy measurements gave the band gap of 4.69 eV for these nanostructures. Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDX) has shown the elemental compositions of gallium oxide deposited samples.

Keywords: β -gallium oxide nanostructures, Powder X-Ray Diffraction, Scanning Electron Microscopy, Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy.

References

1. Sudheer Kumar et al” Adv. Eng. Mater 2014.
2. Mukesh Kumar et al Nanoscale Res. Lett. 12:184, 2017.
3. Hye Jin et al J. Phys. Chem. B, Vol. 107, No. 34, 2003.